

RDMTraining4NFDI

Proposal for the Initialisation Phase of Base4NFDI
Submitted: August 1st, 2024
On behalf of: EduTrain

1. General Information

- Name of proposed Basic Service (in English): Competence Training for Research Data Management
- Acronym of the proposed Basic Service: RDMTraining4NFDI
- Service "subtitle" explaining key functionality: Central services for RDM training material, training formats, didactic concepts and certification.
- Corresponding NFDI Section: Training & Education
- Lead institution: ZB MED - Information Centre for Life Sciences, Gleueler Straße 60, 50931 Cologne
- Name of lead institution principle investigator: Prof. Dr. Konrad U. Förstner, foerstner@zbmed.de
- Participating institutions

Principal Investigator	Institution, location	Contact E-mail	Member in [consortium] ¹	Funding requested [yes no]
Prof. Dr. Mirjam Blümm	Technische Hochschule Köln (TH Köln)	mirjam.bluemm@th-koeln.de	NFDI4Memory	yes
Prof. Dr. Konrad U. Förstner	ZB MED – Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften	foerstner@zbmed.de	NFDI4Microbiota	yes
Prof. Dr. Florian Stahl	Universität Mannheim	florian.stahl@uni-mannheim.de	BERD@NFDI	no
Prof. Dr. Christof Wolf	GESIS - Leibniz Institut für Sozialwissenschaften	christof.wolf@gesis.org	KonsortSWD	no
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¹Name one DFG consortium the institution is or has a route to become a member of and through which funds should be appropriated if this proposal is approved.

Table 1: List of participating institutions

- Planned runtime of the project: 1 year
- Significance: All NFDI consortia are expected to offer training in the knowledge and skills required for research data management (RDM). This training should cover data, software and machine-learning models and be provided to the consortia's own staff, such as data stewards and trainers, as well as to researchers within the respective community. This basic service aims to create a modular collection of foundational RDM training materials together with documented, tried-and-tested training formats and methods. Access to these materials will enable consortia to efficiently develop their own community-specific adaptation of such training and to build capacity quickly. Furthermore, the option of certification will be explored as a means of introducing quality standards to training and documenting the skills acquired by participants.
- Summary of the proposal in English and German

The training of research data management (RDM) skills – including the handling of data, metadata, software and machine learning models in line with FAIR and open science principles – is fundamental to the success of the NFDI (National Research Data Infrastructure). In the initialisation phase, the proposed "RDMTraining4NFDI" basic service aims to provide four solutions to the NFDI consortia and their research communities: (1) modular teaching materials, didactic concepts and workflows for discipline-specific training programmes; (2) two formats (a workshop series and a Summer School) for training data stewards and trainers; (3) a certification concept to document the acquisition of RDM skills in different formats; (4) a communication network of experts in RDM training. The materials will be made freely available through public repositories as open educational resources (OERs) under the CC-BY licence and will be registered in the DALIA platform with a rich set of metadata. Subsequent phases will explore further options such as additional training formats, workflows for integrating new content into the collection and an accreditation process. The basic service will facilitate the efficient ongoing development and dissemination of high-quality training materials and will lay the groundwork for extensive, standardised and certified capacity building. In doing so, it will catalyse the broad adoption of FAIR principles and open science practices by the (German) research community.

Kompetenz im Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM), einschließlich des Umgangs mit Daten, Metadaten, Software und maschinellen Lernmodellen gemäß Open-Science und den FAIR-Prinzipien, ist von grundlegender Bedeutung für den Erfolg der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI). In der Initialisierungsphase zielt der vorgeschlagene

Basisdienst „RDMTraining4NFDI“ darauf ab, den NFDI-Konsortien und ihren Communitys vier Lösungen zur Verfügung zu stellen: (1) modulare Lehrmaterialien, didaktische Konzepte und Workflows für disziplinspezifische Trainingsprogramme, (2) zwei Formate (Workshop-Reihe und Summer School) für die Ausbildung von Data Stewards und Trainern, (3) ein Zertifizierungskonzept und (4) ein Expertennetzwerk für FDM-Ausbildung. Die Materialien werden als offene Bildungsressourcen (OER) unter der CC-BY-Lizenz frei zur Verfügung gestellt und in DALIA inklusive Metadaten registriert. In den folgenden Phasen werden unter anderem weitere Schulungsformate, Arbeitsabläufe für die Integration neuer Inhalte und ein Akkreditierungsverfahren untersucht. Der Basisdienst wird eine kontinuierliche Entwicklung hochwertiger Schulungsmaterialien sowie einen umfassenden und zertifizierten Kompetenzaufbau ermöglichen. Auf diese Weise wird er die Übernahme von FAIR-Prinzipien und Open-Science-Praktiken durch die (deutsche) Forschungsgemeinschaft fördern.

2. State-of-the-Art of Proposed Basic Service

Background and Motivation

The National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) aims to foster professional RDM skills at universities and research institutions nationwide and to support the adoption of FAIR principles². Achieving this goal requires not only the necessary technical infrastructure, but also individuals who possess broad expertise in both generic and domain-specific aspects of RDM and the corresponding didactic skills. Currently, demand for such experts in the research community exceeds their availability³. The race for the best minds is in full swing, as illustrated by the many vacancies in this area within NFDI consortia.⁴ Although some in-service professional qualifications already exist, they are neither numerous nor tailored precisely to the needs of the consortia.⁵ In order to meet the demand for RDM experts in the medium to long term, NFDI consortia need to be able to provide appropriate training to their data stewards, trainers and other staff responsible for RDM.⁶ Between 14th June and 5th July, 2023, the applicants carried out a survey of the NFDI consortia's RDM training needs in the NFDI section Training and Education (EduTrain)⁷. Furthermore, a workshop with representatives from nearly all 26 consortia was held on July 2, 2024 to discuss the proposal and the planned project.⁸ The

² Wilkinson et al., “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.”

³ German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures (RfII), “Digital Competencies – Urgently Needed! – Recommendations on Career and Training Prospects for the Scientific Labour Market.”

⁴ National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) e.V., “Job Advertisements.”

⁵ forschungsdaten.info, “FDM-Professionalisierung.”

⁶ Seidlmayer, E., Hoffmann, F., Dierkes, J., Lindstädt, B., Depping, R., & Förstner, K. U. (2023). Forschung unterstützen - Empfehlungen für Data Stewardship an akademischen Forschungsinstitutionen: Ergebnisse des Projektes DataStew. ZB MED Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften. DOI: 10.4126/FRL01-006441397.

⁷ National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) e.V., “Section Training & Education.”

⁸ Müller, R., Vandendorpe, J., Lindstädt, B., Blümm, M., & Förstner, K. (2024). Report on the Community Workshop for the RDMTraining4NFDI Proposal from July 2 2024. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12772037>

46 representatives of the consortia who responded to the survey expressed a desire for both short-duration and longer-duration certified training formats (chart 5)⁹. As well as one-week workshops and summer schools, they also called for access to intensive training and certificate courses lasting several months (chart 1), especially for the target groups of staff working in science-related infrastructure areas, subject-specific/embedded data stewards and data curators (chart 2). The respondents expressed a preference for a combined course format comprising both asynchronous self-learning units and synchronous meetings (flipped classroom, chart 3). They regard all aspects of RDM (especially legal aspects and metadata) as necessary content. "RDMTraining4NFDI" aims to establish a basic service for the NFDI consortia (Base4NFDI)¹⁰. It meets the Base4NFDI basic service definition by offering a technical-organisational solution that includes software, processes and workflows for creating and delivering RDM training. RDMTraining4NFDI will provide information to consortia on the assistance that is available to adapt training concepts to specific disciplines^{11 12} and will support the consortia in implementing and certifying the training courses themselves. Adaptation of the generic training concepts will initially be carried out for the social and life sciences as well as for the humanities in close cooperation with the NFDI consortia BERD@NFDI¹³, KonsortSWD¹⁴, 4Memory¹⁵ and NFDI4Microbiota¹⁶. Furthermore, the service will compile and provide foundational material on RDM (in its broadest sense and including software and machine learning model management) in adaptable formats under an open licence as OERs.

State-of-the-art

A number of initiatives have sought to compile and evaluate the requirements for RDM training and skills. An excellent overview of these needs can be found in the "Learning objective matrix on the topic of RDM for the target groups students, PhDs and data stewards"¹⁷, which serves as a generic basis for defining and determining teaching content and formats. This matrix was created by members of the Training and Further Education Sub-Working Group of the DINI/nessor Working Group on Research Data and was recently updated as a bilingual version (German/English). It provides a consistent, summarised overview of relevant teaching content and associated learning objectives for various qualification levels based on a number of national and international projects and training concepts in the field of RDM. In terms of didactic skills,

⁹ For all charts please see: <https://th-koeln.sciebo.de/s/JhtdYwZ15Xa5ZbS>

¹⁰ National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) e.V., "Base4NFDI."

¹¹ Paßmann, S., & Söring, S. (2023). Forschungsdatenmanagement in der Psychologie: Fachspezifisches Train-the-Trainer-Konzept (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8113417>

¹² Forschungsdaten.org. "FDNext.", <https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/FDNext>

¹³ BERD@NFDI, "About BERD."

¹⁴ KonsortSWD, "The Consortium."

¹⁵ 4Memory, "The Consortium."

¹⁶ NFDI4Microbiota, "About Us."

¹⁷ Petersen et al., "Lernzielmatrix zum Themenbereich Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) für die Zielgruppen Studierende, PhDs und Data Stewards (V2) [Working Paper]."

both The Carpentries and the “Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management” offer comprehensive train-the-trainer workshops.¹⁸

Status of work results in preparation for the Basic Service

Some NFDI consortia have already applied the aforementioned matrix, in whole or in part, to their subject-specific contexts and target groups. For example, BERD@NFDI and KonsortSWD adapted the learning objective matrix to include learning objectives specific to social science data as part of WP5 of the NFDI section “EduTrain”. In addition, some consortia have already established subject-specific training programmes of their own. For example, GESIS (as an integral part of KonsortSWD) has been offering RDM training for the social sciences since 2013 and contributed to the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide¹⁹ by developing and creating discipline-specific RDM training materials. One of the tasks of BERD@NFDI in the area of “EduTrain” is to develop a subject-specific training programme for subject librarians in economics and social sciences at academic libraries. The aim of the training is to enable them to offer subject-specific advice on the topic of RDM. For this project, BERD@NFDI conducted a needs assessment of the target group.²⁰ In the Data Literacy Task Area of the 4Memory consortium, a mapping has already been created between the RDM matrix of the DIAMANT model²¹, the RDM learning objectives matrix and the TaDiRAH taxonomy²². Meanwhile, NFDI4Microbiota offers numerous RDM and metadata training events as part of its overall training programme, which covers a broad range of topics from basic programming to cloud computing²³. In term of topics, the proposed service will be built upon the certificate course “Research Data Management”²⁴, which was launched in 2021 and is set to run for the fourth time in autumn 2024. Designed and managed by the applicants, this course aims to provide a comprehensive foundation in RDM through 10 modules over 10 months. It covers the essential aspects of implementing open science and FAIR principles at research institutions and universities in alignment with initiatives such as the NFDI and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The course includes a module exploring RDM requirements across six disciplines, which incorporates work carried out by NFDI consortia. The course's popularity is driven by demand for RDM experts and by its certified, modular, part-time format. Initially limited to North Rhine-Westphalia in 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 due to funding, subsequent rounds from 2023 onwards have been open to the entire DACH region. In a further example of its

¹⁸ Biernacka, K., Bierwirth, M., Buchholz, P., Dolzycka, D., Helbig, K., Neumann, J., Odebrecht, C., Wiljes, C., & Wuttke, U. (2020). Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management (3.0) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4071471>

¹⁹ CESSDA Training Team, “CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide.”

²⁰ Schumm, I., & Murcia Serra, J. (2024, May 15). Forschungsdatenmanagement-Grundlagen. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11196891>

²¹ Lemaire, Marina et al., “Das DIAMANT-Modell 2.0.”

²² “TaDiRAH - Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities (version 2.0, 07/2021). <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/en/>.”

²³ <https://nfdi4microbiota.de/training/training>

²⁴ https://www.th-koeln.de/weiterbildung/zertifikatskurs-forschungsdatenmanagement_82048.php

preparatory work, ZB MED has spent several years running training courses in RDM for bio-medicine including its activities as partner in NFDI4Microbiota and NFDI4Health. This training programme is aimed at (bio-)medical researchers of all qualification levels who are interested in learning about best practices in RDM. As well as addressing general aspects of RDM, it also covers (bio-)medicine-specific aspects of RDM, such as privacy issues, and solutions offered by NFDI4Health and NFDI4Microbiota.²⁵ The working group “WP5: Training formats and certificate course” of the NFDI section “Training & Education” was formed in June 2022. It consists of representatives of several NFDI consortia and is led by ZB MED. In one of its main achievements to date, the working group tailored the learning objective matrix to a specific discipline for the target group of data stewards and trainers. Carried out by representatives of BERD@NFDI and KonsortSWD (see also chapter 2), this customisation focused on the social sciences and economics. In the cooperation project FDM@Studium.nrw, TH Köln has built up expertise in designing reusable OER training materials for RDM, which can be used across disciplines to promote RDM competences in Bachelor's and Master's degree programmes.

Current Technical Readiness Level (TRL) of the proposed Basic Service

The proposed basic service will be based on the subject areas covered by the “Research Data Management” certificate course. This has already been tried and tested in three rounds, giving it a high level of maturity (equivalent to TRL 5). Covering all aspects of RDM, the course has undergone rigorous testing to ensure its effectiveness and accuracy of fit and has been meticulously tailored to provide data stewards with the comprehensive knowledge and practical skills required to manage research data throughout its lifecycle. Each module of the course has been thoroughly reviewed and refined by subject-matter experts in the field of data management. Furthermore, the course has been extensively piloted with diverse groups of participants, receiving positive feedback and confirming its adaptability across different disciplines. With its tried-and-tested curriculum and emphasis on best practices, the RDM training course successfully provides participants with the necessary tools to manage data effectively and achieve high maturity in their data management practices. The content is delivered using Markdown source files and the LiaScript dialect, plus GitHub for collaborative working and automatic project building. This proved to be an effective combination in the project `fdm@studium.nrw`, where it ensured flexibility and accessibility.²⁶

Building on the experience of the certificate course, the proposed service will adapt and enhance its training formats, including the Summer School and a one-month series of workshops. These new formats will be developed using insights and feedback from the

²⁵ Vandendorpe and Lindstädt, “Training Workshop on Research Data Management in (Bio-)Medicine.”

²⁶ Blümm, M., Fritsch, K., Bock, S., Prof. Dr. Arning, U., & Prof. Dr. Förstner, K. U. (2024). VL 01 Forschungsdaten. Blended-Learning-Basiskurs „Forschungsdatenmanagement“ (Version 0.1). https://mbluemm.github.io/modul-fdII-thkoeln/texte/VL_01_Forschungsdaten.html

certificate course to ensure they meet the diverse needs of different disciplines. The Summer School will offer an intensive, immersive learning experience, while the one-month series of workshops will provide a more extended and flexible training schedule. By leveraging the proven success and methodology of the certificate course, we aim to create effective and engaging RDM training tailored to various contexts and audiences.

3. SWOT Analysis

Internal	<p>Strengths</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Current profile of the project proposal corresponds to current needs of the community 2. High capacity for flexibility in adapting and creating RDM training thanks to collaboration with NFDI consortia 3. Expertise and experience in developing RDM training formats and teaching materials 4. High degree of national and international networking (specialist scientific fields, political processes and committees) 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High diversity: different disciplines tend to have different requirements and subject cultures 2. Difficult to get balance between build-up of know-how and administrative effort of project support 3. Unclear, insufficiently differentiated performance measures & indicators 4. Marketing the results
External	<p>Opportunities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish discipline-specific RDM training and customisable training concepts in the NFDI 2. Cooperation with NFDI consortia enables coordinated service 3. Clear commitment of NFDI to RDM training and OERs 4. Qualification opportunities and career incentives for NFDI employees 5. Expand cooperative relationship with stakeholders in RDM 6. Ensure high quality training with certification 	<p>Threats</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Different expectations of target groups could lead to products that are not completely coherent (portfolio management) 2. Major dependence on cooperation and support from NFDI consortia 3. High number of temporary employees makes long-term planning, profile building and retention of top performers difficult, resulting in brain drain

Table 2: SWOT analysis

Offering a common foundational RDM training programme as a basic service will enable the efficient development of discipline-specific RDM training programmes building upon shared core content. Different disciplines tend to have different data management requirements and practices; a tailored approach will therefore ensure that researchers receive relevant, targeted training. The service will be designed with flexibility in mind, allowing it to adapt to emerging research practices and technological advances. A joint training concept will also enable the various NFDI consortia to collaborate more effectively, thereby encouraging the sharing of best practices, resources and expertise. Improved collaboration will ensure a more coordinated approach to RDM training across disciplines, avoiding duplication of efforts and fostering a cohesive support network for researchers. By choosing to adopt this programme, the NFDI will demonstrate its commitment to promoting effective RDM practices and open educational resources (OERs), taking it one step closer to its “One NFDI” goal. Such a commitment sends a

strong message about the importance of data stewardship, data sharing and openness in research, helping to promote a culture of responsible data management. The training service will provide qualification opportunities for NFDI employees who are involved in developing and delivering RDM training. Their involvement in designing and conducting the training programme will enhance their expertise, potentially leading to career incentives, greater recognition and professional growth. These benefits will, in turn, serve to attract and retain skilled professionals in the NFDI community, ensuring the sustainability and quality of RDM training initiatives. Overall, an NFDI-wide RDM training programme presents an opportunity to strengthen the research community's data management practices, to foster interdisciplinary collaboration and to build a well-trained workforce capable of effectively managing research data. A centralised certification will lead to a high quality standard of training. By establishing such a programme, the NFDI will increase its impact on research outcomes and contribute to a more open and efficient scientific ecosystem. One of the biggest challenges is the significant diversity among the various disciplines, each of which has its own unique requirements and subject cultures. To overcome this, the service will offer modular, customisable content and adopt three different delivery formats (two in the initialisation phase). In addition to core components applicable to all disciplines, the service will also include specialised modules tailored to the specific RDM needs of each field. To ensure that content is relevant and tailored to subject cultures, the courses will be developed with the help of subject-matter experts from various disciplines. Getting the right balance between the steady build-up of know-how and the administrative effort required to support the basic service also poses a significant challenge. Automating administrative tasks and streamlining workflows can help to reduce the burden on course developers, ensuring a balanced allocation of effort between knowledge building and project support. A further challenge could stem from a failure to adopt clear, properly differentiated performance measures. To avoid this risk, it is essential to define clear and measurable performance indicators from the moment the service is first established. These measures should align with the NFDI's objectives and the specific goals of the RDM training service. Regular evaluation and feedback from participants and stakeholders can help to refine and delineate the performance measures. By continuously monitoring course effectiveness, adjustments can be made to optimise the learning results and adapt the training programme to changing requirements.

4. Working Concept for the Development of the Basic Service

Service initialisation concept

In the initialisation phase, the basic service aims to provide four solutions to the consortia and their research communities: (1) modular teaching materials, didactic concepts and workflows for discipline-specific training programmes; (2) two formats (a workshop series and a Summer School) for training data stewards and trainers; (3) a certification concept to document

the acquisition of RDM skills in different formats; (4) a communication network of experts in RDM training. The blueprint for a modular teaching and training concept will be created as portable content, which can subsequently be adapted by other consortia. It will cover the full spectrum of RDM topics including FAIR principles, metadata, management of privacy-sensitive data, research software, machine learning models and many other aspects, building on the experience of the RDM certificate course run by ZB MED, TH Köln and [fdm.nrw](#)²⁷, the generically oriented learning objectives matrix for RDM²⁸ published by the Training and Further Education Sub-Working Group of the DINI/nesor Working Group on Research Data (AG Forschungsdaten), and The Train-the-Trainer Concept for RDM developed by Biernacka, K., *et al.*²⁹. Content will be created initially in English and then translated to German. Initially, two training formats will be tested and evaluated in practice: a one-month series of workshops and a Summer School. These are aimed specifically at discipline-oriented data stewards³⁰. The basic service is aimed at individuals responsible for training in the NFDI consortia. The goal is to offer them concepts and training formats that will enable them to train data stewards and trainers for their respective consortium (Fig. 1). Centralised support in instructional design, didactics and organisational structuring will be provided by RDMTraining4NFDI based on the Instructor Training from The Carpentries³¹ to ensure the use of evidence-based teaching methods. Furthermore, a trainer network will be established to facilitate knowledge exchange and peer support among trainers. Each participant will receive a certificate of attendance on which the learning objectives are stated. Domain-specific adaptation will initially be carried out for the social sciences in cooperation with the NFDI consortia BERD@NFDI³² and KonsortSWD³³, for the humanities in cooperation with 4Memory³⁴ and for the life sciences in cooperation with NFDI4Microbiota³⁵.

²⁷ Slowig et. al., “Der Zertifikatskurs Forschungsdatenmanagement in NRW. Eine modular aufgebaute Weiterqualifikation für das professionelle Datenmanagement.”

²⁸ Petersen et al., “Lernzielmatrix zum Themenbereich Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) für die Zielgruppen Studierende, PhDs und Data Stewards (V2) [Working Paper].”

²⁹ Biernacka, K., Dockhorn, R., Engelhardt, C., Helbig, K., Jacob, J., Kalová, T., Karsten, A., Meier, K., Mühlichen, A., Neumann, J., Petersen, B., Slowig, B., Trautwein-Bruns, U., Wilbrandt, J., & Wiljes, C. (2023). Train-the-Trainer-Konzept zum Thema Forschungsdatenmanagement (Version 5) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10122153>

³⁰ cf. on the need for embedded data stewards: Seidlmayer et al., “Forschung unterstützen - Empfehlungen für Data Stewardship an akademischen Forschungsinstitutionen : Ergebnisse des Projektes DataStew.”

³¹ The Carpentries, “Instructor Training”

³² BERD@NFDI, “About BERD.”

³³ KonsortSWD, “The Consortium.”

³⁴ 4Memory, “The Consortium.”

³⁵ NFDI4Microbiota, “About Us.”

Fig. 1. Overall structure of RDMTraining4NFDI

Coordination with the cooperating consortia will lead to additional networking with relevant stakeholders in the NFDI and in other initiatives (e.g. train-the-trainer network, DINI/nestor Training and Further Education Sub-Working Group, Base4NFDI liaison officer). Experience sharing and networking with all NFDI consortia will take place within the Training and Education (EduTrain) section. Regular interactions with the Base4NFDI team will ensure alignment of our training efforts with other basic services. This will involve close cooperation with the Service Stewards and offering special workshops, e.g. focused on Personas. The training materials for each module will be made available through public repositories (namely Zenodo) as open educational resources (OERs) using DALIA's metadata schema and a permissive Creative Commons licence (CC-BY).

Development and integration outlook

During the integration phase, the basic service will be adapted for consortia from other scientific fields. RDMTraining4NFDI experts will support discipline-specific implementation and adaptation of the training concepts within the consortia as well as the training courses themselves. Additionally, we will establish a third format of a 10-month-long course building upon our experience of the RDM certificate course developed by TH Köln, ZB MED and fdm.nrw. The results of the EduTrain survey and feedback from the community workshop reveal a clear desire for standardised, certified training. Depending on the findings of the initialisation phase concerning the possibility of providing certification, we will take steps to establish such certification in the integration phase while also exploring the possibility of accrediting institutions

to certify participation themselves. New modules will be developed to address emerging trends, technologies and best practices across different disciplines. Continuous monitoring of performance, participant feedback and the latest RDM trends will inform future updates and to the training courses. In addition, options will be explored to make the service more sustainable by charging fees, and a proposed pricing scheme will be elaborated for this purpose.

Ramping up for Operation

Once the training events have been thoroughly tested and refined, the next step is to roll out the training programme to all NFDI consortia. The rollout process will allow a broader audience to benefit from the training courses, thus promoting a culture of effective data management practices across various research disciplines. Monitoring and support mechanisms will be in place throughout the rollout process to address any issues or challenges that arise. Regular communication will be maintained with the NFDI consortia in order to provide assistance, answer questions and gather feedback. This will ensure smooth implementation and maximise the impact of the RDM workshops. To facilitate the continuous updating and refinement of training materials beyond initial funding cycles, a sustainability plan will be developed.

Risks and challenges

Our RDM certificate course, which will serve as a foundation for the proposed basic service, has been extensively tested and refined. In this context a risk is the dependence on cooperation with NFDI consortia. Interaction with them introduces the possibility of delays or complications in coordinating schedules, aligning goals and accessing necessary resources, potentially impacting the timely delivery of the training programme within the one-year timeframe. Another risk arises from mismatched expectations and varying levels of data management maturity among consortia and participants. Diverse backgrounds and requirements of consortia and individuals could lead to difficulties in tailoring the training to meet the specific needs of each consortium.

5. Work Programme

Overview of work packages

Work package	Deliverables (D) and milestones (M)	Responsible partner
1. Content blueprint	D1.1 Design document based on identified learning materials and objectives (month 2) D1.2 Collection of training materials and guidelines for training delivery (month 9) D1.3 Revised and extended collection of training materials and guidelines for training delivery (month 12) M1.1 Collection of training materials and objectives finalised (month 9)	Lead: TH Köln Partner: ZB MED Cooperation: BERD@NFDI, KonsortSWD, Memory, NFDI4Microbiota, DALIA

WP4: Stakeholder networking and results management				M4.1									M4.2
WP4.1: Networking					D4.1								
WP4.2: Monitoring & reporting													D4.2

5.2.1 WP1 Content blueprint

Lead: TH Köln (8 PM); Partner: ZB MED (2 PM); Cooperation: BERD@NFDI, KonsortSWD, 4Memory, NFDI4Microbiota, DALIA; Duration: months 1-12

Work package 1 will provide a blueprint as requirement analysis for a modular teaching and training concept for the NFDI consortia. The results will include a knowledge base for developing data-type-specific RDM training courses, a guideline for best practices to create and share content as well as a collection of reusable reference materials dealing with course content, formats and adaptation possibilities. We will build upon content already created in all NFDI consortia. The results will serve as the basis for the planned WP2 service of designing and creating data-type-specific training courses. Additionally, synergies with other basic services will be explored to enhance training efforts across the NFDI landscape. This will involve organising a workshop with all basic services to gather training needs and integrating their input into our materials. Each basic service requires documentation, and we aim to attach training formats to these documents where relevant, ensuring that any training needs are met collaboratively.

Milestone M1.1: Collection of training materials and objectives finalised (month 9)

Milestone M1.2: Content blueprint finalised (month 12)

WP1.1 Definition & determination of teaching content and objectives (months 1-2, duration: 2 months): This sub-work package aims to identify existing (data-type-specific) learning materials and data-type-specific learning objectives based on the learning objective matrix.³⁶ To this end, existing preliminary work will be incorporated and evaluated in close consultation with the cooperating consortia. Most of this work will be conducted in the first two months of the project; however, teaching content will continue to be integrated and revised as the project advances.

Deliverable D1.1: Design document based on identified learning materials and objectives (month 2)

WP1.2 Training materials & guidelines (months 3-9, duration: 7 months): In cooperation with four pilot consortia, this sub-work package will involve collecting existing teaching materials & guidelines from all NFDI consortia and, where necessary, creating teaching materials to support the various training events in WP2. The materials will be supplemented by learning

³⁶ Petersen et al., "Lernzielmatrix zum Themenbereich Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) für die Zielgruppen Studierende, PhDs und Data Stewards (V2) [Working Paper]."

resources (e.g. illustrations, quizzes) to support the learning process. To ensure the content can be adapted for other purposes, this step will also include the preparation of didactic concepts for the various training formats and how-to guides to facilitate data-type-specific adaptation of the learning objectives matrix. The didactic concepts will help trainers to structure and prioritise their teaching content and to incorporate methods of engagement. These concepts will be based on The Carpentries Instructor Training³⁷ and the train-the-trainer concept for RDM developed by Biernacka *et al.* 2023.³⁸ The concepts, guidelines and best practices will be published in formats that allow for both internal and external use, properly documented and made accessible as suggested by the “Base4NFDI - Service Documentation Guide”.³⁹ We will utilise the open source OER generator tool LiaScript with Markdown files as source as well as GitHub for collaborative working and automatic building for the documentation and publication, similar to how fdm@studium.nrw have structured their blended-learning course on RDM.⁴⁰

Deliverable D1.2: Collection of training materials and guidelines for training delivery (month 9)

WP1.3 Integration & publication (months 9-12, duration: 3 months): The purpose of this sub-work package is to make all content produced within the project available for re-use on an ongoing basis. Steps include integration in the DALIA portal as well as ongoing publication of all teaching materials on Zenodo or, if applicable, other OER platforms such as Twillo or OERSI⁴¹.

Deliverable D1.3: Revised and extended collection of training materials and guidelines for training delivery (month 12)

5.2.2 WP2 Training format development

Lead: ZB MED (8 PM); Partner: TH Köln (2 PM); Cooperation: DALIA, BERD@NFDI, KonsortSWD, 4Memory, NFDI4Microbiota; Duration: months 7-12

Work Package 2 focuses on the testing, evaluation and subsequent rollout of the RDM training to multiple NFDI consortia. This work package includes setting up a scalable service for establishing data-specific training courses based on the blueprint created in WP1. This service will assist consortia in creating courses with general core content and data-specific adaptations. The content will cover topics including Foundations of RDM, Open Science & Legal Aspects, Hacking & Experimenting with Data, Managing & Sharing (Meta-)Data, Technical Infrastructure, Data & Project Management in Research, and RDM Consulting & Training. Further specifics will

³⁷ The Carpentries, “Instructor Training”

³⁸ Biernacka, K., Dockhorn, R., Engelhardt, C., Helbig, K., Jacob, J., Kalová, T., Karsten, A., Meier, K., Mühlichen, A., Neumann, J., Petersen, B., Slowig, B., Trautwein-Bruns, U., Wilbrandt, J., & Wiljes, C. (2023).

Train-the-Trainer-Konzept zum Thema Forschungsdatenmanagement (Version 5) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10122153>

³⁹ Manske, A., Wittenhorst, T., Ritter, X., & Zänkert, S. (2024). Base4NFDI - Service Documentation Guide (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10634553>

⁴⁰ Blümm, M., Fritsch, K., Bock, S., Prof. Dr. Arning, U., & Prof. Dr. Förstner, K. U. (2024).

VL_01_Forschungsdaten. Blended-Learning-Basiskurs „Forschungsdatenmanagement“ (Version 0.1).

https://mbluemm.github.io/modul-fdII-thkoeln/texte/VL_01_Forschungsdaten.html

⁴¹ <https://www.twillo.de/oer/web/> / <https://oersi.org/resources/>

be defined in WP1 and used for preparing the required teaching material. The first step in this work package will be to conduct a pilot Online Workshop Series and a Summer School with a diverse group of participants from the four initial NFDI consortia. These pilot formats will provide a testing ground to assess the relevance, clarity and practicality of the training content and delivery methods after domain-specific adaptation. The two prototype events are both equally valuable and are designed to address the needs of different user groups in terms of training duration and intensity.

WP2.1 Summer School (months 7-10, duration: 4 months): The on-site Summer School on "Research Data Management for NFDI Consortia" will span one week with a total of 40 hours. It will cover generic RDM topics as well as content tailored to the specific RDM needs of each NFDI consortium. Participants will engage in interactive sessions and provide feedback to enhance the training program. The Summer School aims to foster collaboration and effective data sharing among the consortia. With up to five participants from each of the four consortia, a total of 20 individuals will be involved in this learning experience.

Following the successful completion of the Summer School, a comprehensive evaluation process will be initiated to measure its impact and effectiveness. Surveys will be conducted to collect feedback from participants and trainers in order to assess satisfaction levels, knowledge gain and application of the concepts learned within the participants' research communities. Expert discussions will provide further insight into the effectiveness of the training methods used.

Deliverable D2.1: Evaluation report on the Summer School (month 10)

WP2.2 Online Workshop Series (months 7-10, duration: 4 months): A month-long series of training workshops, in which up to five participants from each of the four consortia will take part, is scheduled for September 2025. This online training format is designed to provide instruction on RDM within a condensed time frame. Through this series of interactive sessions, practical exercises, collaborative learning and self-study phases, participants will enhance their data management skills and gain valuable insights into best practices using open source tools such as Jupyter4NFDI for programming with Python and Hedgedoc for collaborative note taking using open source tools such as Jupyter4NFDI for programming with Python and Hedgedoc for collaborative note taking. The online format allows for flexibility and accessibility, enabling participants to access the training from any location. The total interaction time will be 40 hours, distributed over 4 weeks. Each week will include two five-hour events, one on Monday and one on Friday. Between these days, the participants will be given tasks designed to deepen their understanding of the topics covered.

This evaluation report seeks to collect feedback and insights from the participants on their learning experiences, satisfaction levels and practical application of the acquired knowledge. By

analysing the evaluation data, the project team can identify strengths and areas for improvement, informing future iterations of the online training program.

Deliverable D2.2: Evaluation report on the Online Workshop Series (month 10)

WP2.3 Comparative evaluation (months 11-12, duration: 2 months): This follow-up evaluation of the pilot execution of the two training formats (the Summer School and the Online Workshop Series) aims to compare and analyse the outcomes and impacts of these test runs. By systematically comparing participant feedback, knowledge retention, and the applicability of acquired skills across the different formats, the comparative evaluation will provide valuable insights into which training format resonated best with participants. Additionally, it will shed light on the most effective methods for delivering content and facilitating learning experiences and will help to refine the requirements for both materials and content delivery.

Deliverable D2.3: Comparative evaluation report (month 12)

5.2.3 WP3 Certification development

Lead: TH Köln (3 PM); Partner: ZB MED (2 PM); Cooperation: BERD@NFDI, KonsortSWD, 4Memory, NFDI4Microbiota; Duration: months 1-12

To enhance the impact and recognition of our RDM training program, we will explore different certification options. This will allow us to formally recognize the specialist knowledge acquired by participants in the field of RDM. We will attempt to build upon existing certification models and develop proposals for procedures that can be easily adapted. Implementation of the certification process itself will be part of the subsequent project phase.

Milestone M3.1: Certification formats and process(es) evaluated as a means of facilitating quality standards (month 12)

WP3.1 Identification & definition of certification formats (months 1-6, duration: 6 months):

Work Package 3.1 will identify existing certification types and formats (e.g. micro-degrees, badges⁴² etc.) and assess the potential of those that best recognize participants' completion of specific learning objectives or modules covered in the training. With this in mind, we will investigate opportunities for collaboration with existing certification bodies and work closely with WP4.

Deliverable D3.1: Collection and evaluation of existing certification types and formats (month 6)

WP3.2 Identification & definition of certification processes (months 7-12, duration: 6 months): This sub-work package aims to define a process or processes for our RDM training formats that will enable the introduction of quality standards. To achieve this goal, we will

⁴² See:

<https://www.hrk.de/positionen/beschluss/detail/micro-degrees-und-badges-als-formate-digitaler-zusatzqualifikation/>
(last accessed 12/07/24)

examine existing best practices (e.g. at the ZBIW⁴³ or the University of Vienna⁴⁴) and derive recommended approaches that suit our purpose and that are flexible enough to be adapted to other comparable training programs. The results will offer a useful basis for a future roll-out of RDM training certification and a potential process for accrediting institutions.

Deliverable D3.2: Evaluation of existing certification processes and recommendations for RDM training formats (month 12)

5.2.4 WP4 - Stakeholder networking and results management

Lead: ZB MED (3 PM); Partner: TH Köln (2 PM); Cooperation: DALIA, BERD@NFDI, KonsortSWD, 4Memory, NFDI4Microbiota; Duration: months 1-12

Work package 4 encompasses all coordination and internal communication as well as external communication with relevant stakeholders. It also includes monitoring, documentation and presentation of the overall results and evaluation of the training formats.

WP4.1 Networking with NFDI consortia and further relevant stakeholders (months 1-12, duration: 12 months): The primary purpose of this work package is to coordinate and communicate with the pilot consortia and other NFDI consortia as well as with the EduTrain section and all relevant working groups. As the target group of RDMTraining4NFDI is partially represented and further defined in the EduTrain section, and Work Package 5 Certificate Infrastructure and Training Formats is also part of the section, participation in the section and work package meetings is an important element of the coordination task. In addition, meetings will be held with the pilot consortia, other NFDI consortia and other sections (ELSA, Common Infrastructure, Metadata) to align the content of the training courses and to ensure effective coordination with the Base4NFDI Training Manager, other basic services and DALIA.

In addition to those involved in the NFDI, there are other stakeholders with whom information and coordination activities will be carried out in the form of meetings. These include, for example, the DINI/nestor Working Group on Research Data and, in particular, the Training and Further Education Sub-Working Group. It will also be important to network with the train-the-trainer network, which is currently being set up and coordinated by fdm.nrw, as well as with the selected data competence centres funded by the BMBF and with other relevant organisations (e. g. federal state initiatives for RDM and their training activities).

Deliverable D4.1.1: Stakeholder meeting (online)

⁴³ See: https://www.th-koeln.de/weiterbildung/zertifikatskurse_5882.php (last accessed 12/07/24)

⁴⁴ See: <https://rdm.univie.ac.at/fdm-news-details/news/certificate-course-data-steward-at-the-university-of-vienna-registered-now-open/> (last accessed 12/07/24)

WP4.2 Monitoring, documentation and presentation of results (months 1-12, duration: 12 months): The purpose of WP 4.2 is to monitor and document achievement of the defined goals of WPs 1, 2 and 3. This work package also involves processing and summarising the results of the training evaluations.

Documentation of the processes in WPs 1, 2 and 3 and the results of the training format evaluations will be channelled into a steadily expanding slide deck, which will be used for presentations and the final report. Recommendations for the ongoing design of data- and subject-specific training programmes and the support provided by RDMTraining4NFDI will form a key element of this report.

Deliverable D4.1: Report on the stakeholder meeting

Deliverable D4.2: Final report on the initialisation phase of RDMTraining4NFDI

III Appendix

a) Bibliography and list of references

Sources written or developed by members of the participating institutions in bold:

4Memory. “The Consortium.” Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://4memory.de/partners/>.

BERD@NFDI. “About BERD.” Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://www.berd-nfdi.de/>.

Blümm, M., Fritsch, K., Bock, S., Prof. Dr. Arning, U., & Prof. Dr. Förstner, K. U. (2024). VL_01_Forschungsdaten. Blended-Learning-Basiskurs „Forschungsdatenmanagement“ (Version 0.1).

https://mbluemm.github.io/modul-fdII-thkoeln/texte/VL_01_Forschungsdaten.html

Blümm, Mirjam, Konrad U. Förstner, Marvin Lanczek, Birte Lindstädt, Rabea Müller, Ulrike Nickenig, Stephanie Rehwald, Benjamin Slowig, and Jessica Stegemann. “Der Zertifikatskurs Forschungsdatenmanagement als adaptierbares Aus- und Weiterbildungsangebot,” 2022. <https://doi.org/10.11588/HEIBOOKS.979.C13758>.

Biernacka, K., Dockhorn, R., Engelhardt, C., Helbig, K., Jacob, J., Kalová, T., Karsten, A., Meier, K., Mühlichen, A., Neumann, J., Petersen, B., Slowig, B., Trautwein-Bruns, U., Wilbrandt, J., & Wiljes, C. (2023). Train-the-Trainer-Konzept zum Thema Forschungsdatenmanagement (Version 5) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10122153>

CESSDA Training Team. “CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide,” January 31, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3820473>.

DALIA. “DALIA - Datenkompetenz von Anfang an.” Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://dalia.education/#home>.

forschungsdaten.info. “FDM-Professionalisierung.” Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://forschungsdaten.info/praxis-kompakt/fdm-professionalisierung/>.

German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures (RfII). “Digital Competencies – Urgently Needed! – Recommendations on Career and Training Prospects for the Scientific Labour Market,” n.d. <https://rfii.de/?p=4015>.

KonsortSWD. “The Consortium.” Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/konsortswd/the-consortium/>.

Lemaire, Marina, Gerhards, Lea, Kellendonk, Stefan, and Förster, André. "Das DIAMANT-Modell 2.0: Modellierung des FDM-Referenzprozesses und Empfehlungen Für Die Implementierung Einer Institutionellen FDM-Servicelandschaft," 2020. <https://doi.org/10.25353/UBTR-XXXX-F5D2-FFFB>.

Manske, A., Wittenhorst, T., Ritter, X., & Zänkert, S. (2024). Base4NFDI - Service Documentation Guide (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10634553>.

Müller, R., Vandendorpe, J., Lindstädt, B., Blümm, M., & Förstner, K. (2024). Report on the Community Workshop for the RDMTraining4NFDI Proposal from July 2 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12772037>

National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) e.V. "Base4NFDI." Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://base4nfdi.de/>.

———. "Job Advertisements." Accessed July 26, 2023. <https://www.nfdi.de/jobs/?lang=en>.

———. "Section Training & Education." Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://www.nfdi.de/section-edutrain/?lang=en>.

NFDI4Microbiota. "About Us." Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://nfdi4microbiota.de/about/>.

Paßmann, S., & Söring, S. (2023). Forschungsdatenmanagement in der Psychologie: Fachspezifisches Train-the-Trainer-Konzept (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8113417>

Petersen, Britta, Claudia Engelhardt, Tanja Hörner, Juliane Jacob, Tatiana Kvetnaya, Andreas Mühlichen, Hermann Schranzhofer, et al. "Lernzielmatrix zum Themenbereich Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) für die Zielgruppen Studierende, PhDs und Data Stewards (V2) [Working Paper]." Zenodo, June 14, 2023. <https://zenodo.org/record/8010617>.

Schumm, I., & Murcia Serra, J. (2024, May 15). Forschungsdatenmanagement-Grundlagen. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11196891>

Seidlmayer, Eva, Fabian Hoffmann, Jens Dierkes, Birte Lindstädt, Ralf Depping, and Konrad Ulrich Förstner. "Forschung unterstützen - Empfehlungen für Data Stewardship an akademischen Forschungsinstitutionen : Ergebnisse des Projektes DataStew," 2023. <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006441397>.

Slowig, Benjamin, Mirjam Blümm, Konrad U. Förstner, Marvin Lanczek, Birte Lindstädt, Rabea Müller, Ulrike Nickenig, Stephanie Rehwald, and Lioba Schreyer. "Der Zertifikatskurs Forschungsdatenmanagement in NRW: Eine modular aufgebaute Weiterqualifikation für das professionelle Datenmanagement." *o-bib. Das offene*

***Bibliotheksjournal / Herausgeber VDB* 9, no. 3 (August 16, 2022): 1–10.**
<https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/5833>.

TaDiRAH. “Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities (v. 2.0, 07/2021).”
Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/en/>.

Technische Hochschule Köln. “Zertifikatskurs Forschungsdatenmanagement.”
Accessed July 26, 2023.
https://www.th-koeln.de/weiterbildung/zertifikatskurs-forschungsdatenmanagement_82048.php.

The Carpentries. “Instructor Training.” Accessed 11 July, 2024.

———. “Zertifikatskurs ‘Forschungsdatenmanagement’: Modulhandbuch.” Accessed
July 26, 2023.
https://www.th-koeln.de/mam/downloads/deutsch/weiterbildung/zbiw/angebote/zbiw_modulhandbuch_zk_fdm_2023-24.pdf.

Vandendorpe, Justine, and Birte Lindstädt. “Training Workshop on RDM in (Bio-)Medicine,” 2023. <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006399944>.

Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.” *Scientific Data* 3, no. 1 (March 15, 2016): 160018.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

ZBIW (Technische Hochschule Köln). “Wir über uns.” Accessed July 26, 2024.
https://www.th-koeln.de/weiterbildung/wir-ueber-uns_5869.php.